

D1.9 Research/Industry Workshop

WP1 Project Management, Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication

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PROJECT DETAILS AND DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

PROJECT DETAILS

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DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

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Authors	Elena Bellotti, Giuseppe Barillaro
Contributors	/
Reviewers	Thierry Djenizian, Jorge Morgado
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DISSEMINATION LEVEL

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SEN	Sensitive — limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
EU classified	EU classified — RESTREINT-UE/EU-RESTRICTED, CONFIDENTIEL-UE/EU-CONFIDENTIAL, SECRET-UE/EU-SECRET under Decision 2015/444	

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Author	Description of Change
0.1	11/04/2025	Elena Bellotti	First Release
0.2	16/04/2025	Giuseppe Barillaro	Draft Review
0.3	18/04/2025	Thierry Djenizian	Internal Review
0.4	19/04/2025	Elisabetta Mazzotta	Internal Review
1.0	22/04/2025	Eelna Bellotti	Final Release

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GLOSSARY OF ACRONYMS

MRS	Materials Research Society
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DISCLAIMER

Views and opinions expressed in this Deliverable are those of the author only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The aim of the deliverable D1.9 Research/Industry Workshop is to report on the organization of a scientific dissemination event aimed at promoting scientific exchange and increasing the visibility of the RESORB project within the international research community.

To achieve this, Giuseppe Barillaro (University of Pisa, RESORB Project Coordinator) co-organized the international symposium entitled “Transient and Bioresorbable Materials for Sensing and Therapeutic Applications”, held during the 2025 MRS Spring Meeting and Exhibition, which took place in Seattle, Washington (USA) from April 7, 2025 to April 11, 2025.

The symposium provided an international platform for scientific exchange among researchers and industrials working in the field of biodegradable and transient materials, with a focus on their application in sensing and therapeutic systems. The event brought together internationally recognized professors and scientists from leading universities and research institutes. Topics included materials design, bioresorbable electronics, fabrication strategies, integration of transient systems for biomedical use, as well as the impact the degradation products have on the environmental and biological systems.

The organization of this symposium contributed to the broader dissemination and impact strategy of the project and reinforced its presence within the international scientific and industrial community.

2. SYMPOSIUM RATIONALE AND SCIENTIFIC CONTEXT

As part of the activities foreseen in WP1 Project Management, Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication, the organization of a scientific symposium was envisioned as strategic tool to support both the dissemination goals and the broader integration of the RESORB project within the international research landscape. The thematics of the symposium closely aligned with the project core objectives, particularly in the areas of transient materials for sensing device, device integration, and therapeutic applications.

By gathering a diverse group of researchers from multiple institutions and countries, the symposium offered a broader scientific context in which RESORB project could be framed, discussed, and compared with complementary approaches developed worldwide.

The event also contributed to strengthening the project visibility, encouraging academic networking, and identifying potential future synergies with related scientific efforts.

3. SYMPOSIUM ORGANIZATION AND SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

The symposium entitled Transient and Bioresorbable Materials for Sensing and Therapeutic Applications was co-organized by Giuseppe Barillaro (University of Pisa, RESORB Project Coordinator) together with Clementine Boutry (Delft University of Technology), Alex Chortos (Purdue University), and Helen Tran (University of Toronto). It was held from April 7, 2025 to April 9, 2025. Below is the official flyer, which was used to promote the event through the MRS platform and within the scientific community.

2025 MRS SPRING MEETING & EXHIBIT
April 7-11, 2025 | Seattle, Washington

CALL FOR PAPERS
Abstract Submission Opens
Tuesday, September 17, 2024
Abstract Submission Closes
Thursday, October 17, 2024 (11:59 PM ET)

Symposium SU06: Degradable Materials and Devices -

The degradation of devices is increasingly becoming a critical consideration for the sustainability of devices used outside the body and the functionality of medical devices used inside the body. Degradable medical devices that can be implanted or injected enable new treatment approaches and monitoring concepts without the need for surgery to remove the devices. For devices used outside the body, degradable materials are sought to reduce the accumulation of waste, which is particularly important for waste streams that produce toxic degradation products, exemplified by electronic devices.

This symposium brings together expertise in all areas of degradable materials and devices, including materials discovery, device engineering, and the impact of degradation products in the body or the environment. Devices should have stable functional properties until their function is complete, which can range from days for implantable devices to several years for IoT devices. This has motivated the development of materials that degrade on demand or in specific conditions, such as self-immolative polymers and pH-dependent degradation of nanomaterials. A key question the community is seeking to address is how to achieve performance comparable to traditional devices using degradable materials. Solutions include device optimization and improved understanding of the effect of manufacturing on composites and multilayered materials. As emphasized by increasing awareness of microplastics, understanding the effect of the degradation products will be a critical future challenge. The development of degradable devices will ultimately enable unprecedented capabilities in medical diagnostics and treatments while providing a route towards cost effective and sustainable consumer devices.

Topics will include:

- Chemistry of degradable polymers
- Materials processing to tune degradation
- Performance of degradable composites
- Performance of electronic devices made of degradable materials
- Sensors and actuators made of degradable materials
- Degradable batteries and power sources
- Degradable optical devices
- Degradable environmental sensors
- Degradable devices for medical applications
- Food monitoring degradable packaging
- Degradable wireless antennas and IoT applications
- Impact of degradation products on environmental and biological systems

Invited speakers include:

Matt Becker	Duke University, USA	Thanh Duc Nguyen	University of Connecticut, USA
Michael Dickey	University of Texas, Austin, USA	Ji-Ho Park	KAIST, Republic of Korea
Thierry Djenizian	Ecole Des Mines, France	Rahim Rahimi	Purdue University, USA
Elizabeth Gillies	University of Western Ontario, Canada	Ritu Raman	Massachusetts Institute of Technology, USA
Suk-Won Hwang	Korea University - Korea Institute of Science and Technology (KU-KIST), Republic of Korea	John Rogers	Northwestern University, USA
Mihai Irimia-Vladu	University of Linz, Austria	Simon Rondeau Gagne	Windsor University, Canada
Martin Kaltenbrunner	Johannes Kepler University Linz, Austria	Michael Sailor	University of California, San Diego, USA
Seung-Kyun Kang	Seoul National University, Republic of Korea	Gregory Whiting	University of Colorado Boulder, USA
Gurvinder Singh Khinda	GE, USA	Lan Yin	Tsinghua University, China

Symposium Organizers

<p>Clementine Boutry Delft University of Technology Department of Microelectronics Netherlands Tel 31-15-27-89893, C.M.F.Viellard-Boutry@tudelft.nl</p> <p>Giuseppe Barillaro University of Pisa Information Engineering Department Italy Tel 39-050-2217-601, giuseppe.barillaro@unipi.it</p>	<p>Alex Chortos Purdue University Mechanical Engineering USA Tel (650) 799-0093, achorotos@purdue.edu</p> <p>Helen Tran University of Toronto Chemistry Canada Tel (416) 946-5763, tran@utoronto.ca</p>
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The symposium was part of the official MRS 2025 Spring Meeting scientific program and offered a multidisciplinary agenda focused on the design, fabrication, integration, and application of biodegradable materials and devices. Special attention was devoted to their use in therapeutic and sensing systems, as well as to the environmental and biological implication of their degradation.

The scientific program consisted of seven sessions, which included: i) invited talks by internationally recognized experts from leading universities and research institutions; ii) oral presentations selected through abstract submissions; iii) a poster session that allowed additional researchers, included early-career scientists, to present and discuss their work. A detailed list of all presentations, including titles, authors, and affiliations is provided in Annex 1.

4. AUDIENCE AND SPEAKERS

The symposium attracted a diverse group of attendees from across the international scientific community. Indeed, it was well attended, with an estimated 70 participants on the first day, and around 40 participants on the second and third day. This presence across the sections reflects the strong interest in the topic and the quality of the scientific program.

The invited and contributing speakers came from a wide range of countries, underlining the international scope of the event. The pie chart below (Figure 1) illustrates the percentage distribution of speakers by country of affiliation.

Figure 1. Percentage distribution of speakers by country of affiliation

The symposium addressed a broad spectrum of topics, spanning fundamentals materials science, device engineering, biomedical applications, and environmental considerations. The

pie chart below (Figure 2) summarizes the main thematic areas represented in the presentations.

Figure 2. Main topics represented in the presentations

The variety of contributions highlights the interdisciplinary nature of the symposium and the relevance of presented research to the RESORB project thematic areas.

5. RESORB PROJECT CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE SYMPOSIUM

The RESORB project was actively represented within the scientific program of the symposium through high quality oral contributions and invited presentations from its partners and collaborators. These talks provided an in-depth overview of key research lines within the project, covering topics such as implantable sensors for clinical monitoring, transient energy storage systems, and in vivo validations of bioresorbable devices. Below is a summary of the main contributions:

- Dr. Eleonora Vandini (University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy)

Oral presentation entitled “How to establish if a device is bioresorbable or biocompatible in vivo”.

This presentation addressed the critical need for standardized evaluation of bioresorbable medical devices, with a focus on their biocompatibility and long-term safety in vivo. Dr. Vandini proposed a rigorous protocol combining in vivo and ex vivo methods to assess toxicity and degradation of implanted devices over a three-month period.

The study showed the evaluation of a bioresorbable pH sensor and a rechargeable battery implanted subcutaneously in mice. The analysis included behavioural assessments, body weight and temperature monitoring, open-field testing for anxiety and locomotion, blood biomarkers of hepatic toxicity, and detailed histopathological examination of major organs.

The comprehensive approach demonstrated the feasibility of confirming both the absence of toxic effects and the complete bioresorption of the device materials. This work contributes directly to RESORB's objective of developing safe and effective bioresorbable technologies for real-time sensing in vivo.

- Dr. Martina Corsi (University of Pisa, Italy)

Oral presentation entitled "Implantable and biodegradable chemical sensors for real-time monitoring of clinical/diagnostic markers with high spatial and temporal accuracy"

Martina Corsi presented a cutting-edge platform of nanostructured porous silica membranes for use as implantable, biodegradable chemical sensors. These devices are designed to continuously monitor key biochemical parameters, such as pH and drug concentration, directly at the site of interest within the body.

The talk focused on two sensor prototypes: one for pH detection, relevant for monitoring inflammation or cancer-related acidosis, and one for tracking local concentrations of the chemotherapeutic drug doxorubicin. The sensors demonstrated high sensitivity, biocompatibility, and fully bioresorbable behaviour, degrading naturally after their functional lifespan. This contribution illustrated the potential of RESORB technologies to support personalized medicine by enabling temporary, implantable diagnostic tools that require no retrieval surgery and provide real-time feedback for treatment optimization.

- Prof. Thierry Djenizian (Ecole des Mines Saint-Etienne, France)

Distinguished Invited Speaker. Oral presentation entitled "Bioresorbable Na-ion battery for temporary medical devices"

Prof. Djenizian presented a fully bioresorbable, all-solid-state sodium-ion battery developed as a power source for temporary implantable medical devices. The battery, made entirely of biocompatible materials, demonstrated excellent electrochemical performance and a finely tunable degradation profile depending on the encapsulation thickness.

Toxicological evaluation in vivo confirmed the safety of the device over a three-month implantation period. Additionally, wireless inductive recharging was demonstrated through the skin, showcasing its potential for real-world clinical application.

This invited talk aligned closely with RESORB focus on the integration of transient power sources for biodegradable sensing systems, and highlighted the importance of energy autonomy in the next generation of bioresorbable devices.

These contributions effectively highlighted the excellence and innovation of the RESORB project, positioning its research activities at the forefront of the international discussion on transient and bioresorbable technologies. By addressing key challenges related to device biocompatibility, real-time in vivo monitoring, and energy autonomy, the presentations not only highlighted the project core objectives but also fostered meaningful exchange with the broader academic community.

6. RESORB AWARD AT THE SYMPOSIUM

In order to recognize excellence and highlight outstanding contributions aligned with the objectives of the RESORB project, a Distinguished Speaker Award was conferred during the

symposium to Prof. Thierry Djenizian (École des Mines de Saint-Étienne, France) for his pioneering work on bioresorbable energy storage devices. Prof. Djenizian's research represents a major advance in the field, demonstrating the feasibility of fully biodegradable, rechargeable sodium-ion batteries with tunable degradation profiles and validated in vivo safety.

This award underscored both the scientific excellence of his contribution and the critical role of energy autonomy as a key enabling technology for future implantable and biodegradable medical devices. By granting this distinction, the RESORB consortium reaffirmed its commitment to fostering innovation and collaboration at the interface of materials science, bioelectronics, and biomedical applications.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The organization of the symposium within the 2025 MRS Spring Meeting successfully fulfilled the objective of the Deliverable D1.9 by promoting scientific dissemination, visibility, and academic engagement in the field of degradable materials and devices. Through a high-quality program, international participation, and contributions from RESORB partners, the event fostered knowledge exchange and positioned the project within a global research context. The symposium served as an effective platform to communicate project-related advances and strengthen connections with the scientific community.

8. ANNEX 1

Session Information							
SESSION TITLE: SU06.01: Materials Synthesis and Processing							
SESSION TYPE: Oral							
SESSION DAY & DATE: Mon 4/07/2025 8:30 AM							
SESSION DURATION: 180							
SESSION LOCATION: Summit, Level 4, Room 448							
SESSION HOST: Session Chair: Alex Chortos Session Chair: Giuseppe Barillaro							
SESSION TOPIC: SU06: Degradable Materials and Devices							
SESSION ABBREVIATION: SU06.01							
Control ID	Final ID	Title	Presenting Author	Presentation Type	Start/end time	PRESENTER (COUNTRY ONLY)	SESSION ABSTRACT DURATION
4204835	SU06.01.01	Soft, Resorbable Materials for Bioelectronics	Hwang, Suk-Won	Invited Speaker	8:30 AM 9:00 AM	Korea (the Republic of)	30
4204172	SU06.01.02	Biodegradable Piezoelectric Nanofibers for Medical Applications	Nguyen, Thanh	MRS Communications Early Career Distinguished Presenter	9:00 AM 9:30 AM	United States	30
		BREAK			9:30 AM 10:00 AM		30
4207196	SU06.01.03	Green Laser-Induced Graphene from Biodegradable Almond Shell Composite for Sensors Application	Bressi, Anna Chiara	Oral Presentation Preferred	10:00 AM 10:15 AM	Italy	15
4207202	SU06.01.04	From Corn Starch to Magnetic Laser-Induced Graphene Nanocomposite	Bressi, Anna Chiara	Oral Presentation Preferred	10:15 AM 10:30 AM	Italy	15
4206146	SU06.01.05	Leveraging Bio-Inspired and Dynamic Chemistry to Develop Soft and Degradable Thin-Film Transistors	Rondeau-Gagne, Simon	Invited Speaker	10:30 AM 11:00 AM	Canada	30
4205231	SU06.01.06	Recyclable Vitrimers for Electronic Applications—From Circuit Boards to Charging Cables	Biswal, Agni Kumar	Oral Presentation Preferred	11:00 AM 11:15 AM	United States	15
4207630	SU06.01.07	Comprehensive Study of Substrate van der Waals Force Effect on the Stability of Violet Phosphorus	Singh, Sarabpreet	Oral Presentation Preferred	11:15 AM 11:30 AM	United States	15

Session Information							
SESSION TITLE: SU06.02: Materials Processing and Functionalization							
SESSION TYPE: Oral							
SESSION DAY & DATE: Mon 4/07/2025 1:30 PM							
SESSION DURATION: 135							
SESSION LOCATION: Summit, Level 4, Room 448							
SESSION HOST: Session Chair: Suk-Won Hwang Session Chair: Thanh Nguyen							
SESSION TOPIC: SU06: Degradable Materials and Devices							
SESSION ABBREVIATION: SU06.02							
Control ID	Final ID	Title	Presenting Author	Presentation Type	Start/end time	PRESENTER (COUNTRY ONLY)	SESSION ABSTRACT DURATION
4204357	SU06.02.01	Liquid Metals as Tools for Creating Degradable Devices	Dickey, Michael	Invited Speaker	1:30 PM 2:00 PM	United States	30
4229711	SU06.02.02	Electronic-Free Wireless Sensors for Subsoil Moisture and Microbial Activity Monitoring	Rahimi, Rahim	Invited Speaker	2:00 PM 2:30 PM	United States	30
		BREAK			2:30 PM 3:00 PM		30
4200247	SU06.02.03	Forest-Based Biodegradable Foam for Thermal Insulation	Simoes, Monica	Oral Presentation Preferred	3:00 PM 3:15 PM	Portugal	15
4207952	SU06.02.04	Degradable Conductive Plastics with Liquid Metal-Vitrimer Composites	Worch, Josh	Oral Presentation Preferred	3:15 PM 3:30 PM	United States	15
4208817	SU06.02.05	Characterizing the Environment Degradation of Thermoplastic Materials for a Novel Semi-Transparent Bifacial Solar Panel via Gaussian Process Regression	McGraw, Duncan	Oral Presentation Preferred	3:30 PM 3:45 PM	United States	15

Session Information							
SESSION TITLE: SU06.03: Devices for Medical Applications I							
SESSION TYPE: Oral							
SESSION DAY & DATE: Mon 4/07/2025 4:15 PM							
SESSION DURATION: 90							
SESSION LOCATION: Summit, Level 4, Room 448							
SESSION HOST: Session Chair: Michael Dickey Session Chair: Rahim Rahimi							
SESSION TOPIC: SU06: Degradable Materials and Devices							
SESSION ABBREVIATION: SU06.03							
Control ID	Final ID	Title	Presenting Author	Presentation Type	Start/end time	PRESENTER (COUNTRY ONLY)	SESSION ABSTRACT DURATION
4207112	SU06.03.01	How to Establish if a Device is Bioresorbable and Biocompatible <i>In Vivo</i>	Vandini, Eleonora	Oral Presentation Preferred	4:15 PM 4:30 PM	Italy	15
4201101	SU06.03.02	Magnesium-Sputtered Collagen Nerve Conduits Regulate Magnesium Ion Release to Promote Peripheral Nerve Regeneration	Kim, Hyewon	Oral Presentation Preferred	4:30 PM 4:45 PM	Korea (the Republic of)	15
4207547	SU06.03.03	Degradation Kinetics, Mechanisms and Antioxidant Activity of PCL-Based Scaffolds with <i>In Situ</i> Grown Nanohydroxyapatite on Graphene Oxide Nanoscrolls	Mambiri, Lillian	Oral Presentation Preferred	4:45 PM 5:00 PM	United States	15
4205261	SU06.03.04	Implantable and Biodegradable Chemical Sensors for Real Time Monitoring of Clinical/Diagnostic Markers with High Spatial and Temporal Accuracy	Corsi, Martina	Oral Presentation Preferred	5:00 PM 5:15 PM	Italy	15
4274298	SU06.03.05	The Design and Development of Degradable Biomaterials of Different Sizes and Formulations for Biomedical Applications from Natural Polymer Polygalacturonic Acid	Sahiner, Nurettin	Oral Presentation Preferred	5:15 PM 5:30 PM	Turkey	15
4277855	SU06.03.06	Dry-Phase Photodegradation of Benzene, Toluene and Xylene (BTX) Using Cu-Doped TiO ₂ Under LED Light Irradiation	Lee, Caroline Sunyong	Oral Presentation Preferred	5:30 PM 5:45 PM	Korea (the Republic of)	15

Session Information							
SESSION TITLE: SU06.04: Devices for Medical Applications II							
SESSION TYPE: Oral							
SESSION DAY & DATE: Tue 4/08/2025 10:30 AM							
SESSION DURATION: 75							
SESSION LOCATION: Summit, Level 4, Room 448							
SESSION HOST: Session Chair: Alex Chortos							
SESSION HOST: Session Chair: Giuseppe Barillaro							
SESSION TOPIC: SU06: Degradable Materials and Devices							
SESSION ABBREVIATION: SU06.04							
Control ID	Final ID	Title	Presenting Author	Presentation Type	Start/end time	PRESENTER (COUNTRY ONLY)	SESSION ABSTRACT DURATION
4223519	SU06.04.01	Chemistry of Porous Silicon to Enable Degradable Drug Delivery Systems	Sailor, Michael	Invited Speaker	10:30 AM 11:00 AM	United States	30
4204253	SU06.04.02	Biodegradable Materials for Peripheral Neural Interfaces	Yin, Lan	MRS Communications Early Career Distinguished Presenter	11:00 AM 11:30 AM	China	30
4209707	SU06.04.03	Multifunctional, Physically Transient Devices— Supercapacitors, Triboelectric Nanogenerators and Capacitive Sensors	Unalan, Husnu	Oral Presentation Preferred	11:30 AM 11:45 AM	Turkey	15

Session Information							
SESSION TITLE: SU06.05: Biodegradable Devices and Sensors							
SESSION TYPE: Oral							
SESSION DAY & DATE: Tue 4/08/2025 1:30 PM							
SESSION DURATION: 165							
SESSION LOCATION: Summit, Level 4, Room 448							
SESSION HOST: Session Chair: Michael Sailor							
SESSION HOST: Session Chair: Lan Yin							
SESSION TOPIC: SU06: Degradable Materials and Devices							
SESSION ABBREVIATION: SU06.05							
Control ID	Final ID	Title	Presenting Author	Presentation Type	Start/end time	PRESENTER (COUNTRY ONLY)	SESSION ABSTRACT DURATION
4186977	SU06.05.01	Degradable, Wireless Optoelectronics for Electrotherapy	Rogers, John	Invited Speaker	1:30 PM 2:00 PM	United States	30
4203731	SU06.05.02	Biodegradable and Self-Deployable Electronics for Minimally Invasive Brain Interfaces	Kang, Seung-Kyun	Invited Speaker	2:00 PM 2:30 PM	Korea (the Republic of)	30
		BREAK			2:30 PM 3:00 PM		30
4205107	SU06.05.03	Biodegradable and Printed Impedance-Based pH Sensors for Agricultural Monitoring	Cameron, Joseph	Oral Presentation Preferred	3:00 PM 3:15 PM	United Kingdom	15
4206690	SU06.05.04	Development of Leaf-Based Hydrovoltaic Device	Viradia, Neha	Oral Presentation Preferred	3:15 PM 3:30 PM	United States	15
4209569	SU06.05.05	Biodegradable Printed Sensors for <i>In Situ</i> Evaluation of Soil Microbial Decomposition Activity	Whiting, Gregory	Invited Speaker	3:30 PM 4:00 PM	United States	30
4209956	SU06.05.06	Photopatternable, Degradable and Performant Polyimide Network Substrates for E-Waste Mitigation	Wang, Chen	Oral Presentation Preferred	4:00 PM 4:15 PM	United States	15

Session Information							
SESSION TITLE: SU06.06: Poster Session: Degradable Materials and Devices							
SESSION TYPE: Poster							
SESSION DAY & DATE: Tue 4/08/2025 5:00 PM							
SESSION DURATION: 120							
SESSION LOCATION: Summit, Level 2, Flex Hall C							
SESSION HOST: Session Chair: Seung-Kyun Kang							
Session Chair: Gregory Whiting							
SESSION TOPIC: SU06: Degradable Materials and Devices							
SESSION ABBREVIATION: SU06.06							
Control ID	Final ID	Title	Presenting Author	Presentation Type	Start/end time	PRESENTER (COUNTRY ONLY)	SESSION ABSTRACT DURATION
4203602	SU06.06.01	Laser Direct Writing of Conductive Structures on Marine-Biodegradable Polymer Composite Sheets	Kato, Mari	Poster Presentation Preferred	5:00 PM 7:00 PM	Japan	0
4205985	SU06.06.02	Adhesion-Assisted Laser Ablation for the Fabrication of Bioresorbable Electronics	Seo, Hyungho	Poster Presentation Preferred	5:00 PM 7:00 PM	Korea (the Republic of)	0
4206917	SU06.06.03	Soft and Rapidly Biodegradable 3D-Printable Electronics	Park, Joo-Hyeon	Poster Presentation Preferred	5:00 PM 7:00 PM	Korea (the Republic of)	0
4208762	SU06.06.04	Mullite-Type O8 $EMBO_4$ Phases ($E = Pb, Sn; M = Al, Ga, V, Cr, Fe, Mn$) as Exciton Source for Photo-Catalytic Processes on Activated Carbon	Gesing, Thorsten	Poster Presentation Preferred	5:00 PM 7:00 PM	Germany	0
4201962	SU06.06.05	Novel SERS DNA Biosensor Using Nanostructured GaN Template and Thin Metal Film for Mutation Detection in Clinical Samples	Michalowska, Aleksandra	Poster Presentation Preferred	5:00 PM 7:00 PM	Poland	0
4210113	SU06.06.06	Chemo-Thermo-Mechanical Characterization of Cellulose Acetate Microfibers	Wilkinson, Eric	Poster Presentation Preferred	5:00 PM 7:00 PM	United States	0
4273888	SU06.06.07	Biodegradable Temperature Soil Sensors via Stimuli-Responsive Polymers	Micklin, Elsa	Poster Presentation Preferred	5:00 PM 7:00 PM	United States	0
4277572	SU06.06.08	Biodegradable Neuromorphic Memristor Arrays with Enhanced Linearity and Synaptic Plasticity for Implantable Bioelectronics	Kwak, Kyungmoon	Poster Presentation Preferred	5:00 PM 7:00 PM	Korea (the Republic of)	0
4278333	SU06.06.09	High Temperature Melt Electrowriting	Luposchinsky, Simon	Poster Presentation Preferred	5:00 PM 7:00 PM	Japan	0
4279017	SU06.06.10	High-Temperature Corrosion Behavior of Ferritic Stainless Steels Under Ammonia-Fueled SOFC Conditions Environments	Joh, Dong Woo	Poster Presentation Preferred	5:00 PM 7:00 PM	Korea (the Republic of)	0

Session Information							
SESSION TITLE: SU06.07: Emerging Developments							
SESSION TYPE: Oral							
SESSION DAY & DATE: Wed 4/09/2025 9:00 AM							
SESSION DURATION: 180							
SESSION LOCATION: Summit, Level 4, Room 448							
SESSION HOST: Session Chair: Alex Chortos Session Chair: Giuseppe Barillaro							
SESSION TOPIC: SU06: Degradable Materials and Devices							
SESSION ABBREVIATION: SU06.07							
Control ID	Final ID	Title	Presenting Author	Presentation Type	Start/end time	PRESENTER (COUNTRY ONLY)	SESSION ABSTRACT DURATION
4203165	SU06.07.01	Self-Immolative Polymers—Chemical Designs and Applications	Gillies, Elizabeth	Invited Speaker	9:00 AM 9:30 AM	Canada	30
4204441	SU06.07.02	Biodegradable Porous Silicon Materials for Therapeutic Applications	Park, Ji Ho	Invited Speaker	9:30 AM 10:00 AM	Korea (the Republic of)	30
		BREAK			10:00 AM 10:30 AM		30
4278792	SU06.07.03	Mechanically Tunable and Cellularly Adhesive Highly Entangled Hydrogels with Degradable Crosslinks	Sunday, Alex	Oral Presentation Preferred	10:30 AM 10:45 AM	United States	15
4209696	SU06.07.04	Influence of Water on Printed Nanocellulose Dielectric Performance	Smith, Brittany	Oral Presentation Preferred	10:45 AM 11:00 AM	United States	15
4202527	SU06.07.05	Biohybrid and Biodegradable Soft Robots Capable of Multi Degree-of-Freedom Motion	Raman, Ritu	Invited Speaker	11:00 AM 11:30 AM	United States	30
4204519	SU06.07.06	Bioresorbable Na-ion Battery for Temporary Medical Devices	Djenizian, Thierry	JMR Distinguished Invited Speaker	11:30 AM 12:00 PM	France	30